

Brain region	LTI quails		STI quails		Statistical values		
	Left-H	Right-H	Left-H	Right-H	Line	Hemisphere	Interaction
Extended amygdala	0.198 ± 0.009	0.174 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.013	0.184 ± 0.006	F=2.666 p=0.12	F=78.924 p<0.0001	F=3.2 p=0.091
Frontoamygdaloid tract	0.055 ± 0.004	0.05 ± 0.005	0.051 ± 0.003	0.049 ± 0.003	F=2.924 p=0.104	F=10.265 p=0.005	F=0.796 p=0.384
Amygdalohypothalamic tract	0.024 ± 0.002	0.022 ± 0.003	0.024 ± 0.002	0.023 ± 0.003	F=0.021 p=0.885	F=9.203 p=0.007	F=0.034 p=0.855
Anterior amygdala area ##	0.074 ± 0.002	0.087 ± 0.005	0.069 ± 0.006	0.083 ± 0.008			
Arcopallium-amygdaloïd complex #	0.572 ± 0.036	0.646 ± 0.044	0.573 ± 0.027	0.637 ± 0.031			
Amygdaloïd taenial area #	0.094 ± 0.004	0.096 ± 0.008	0.092 ± 0.007	0.089 ± 0.007			
Bed nucleus of stria terminalis	0.193 ± 0.012	0.231 ± 0.008	0.192 ± 0.013	0.221 ± 0.013	F=1.302 p=0.269	F=280.949 p<0.0001	F=5.093 p=0.037
Substantia nigra	0.082 ± 0.007	0.083 ± 0.007	<u>0.093 ± 0.007</u>	<u>0.099 ± 0.007</u>	F=20.415 p=0.0003	F=12.602 p=0.002	F=6.591 p=0.019
Thalamus	0.364 ± 0.018	0.338 ± 0.02	<u>0.399 ± 0.014</u>	<u>0.365 ± 0.018</u>	F=18.788 p=0.0004	F=83.755 p<0.0001	F=1.688 p=0.21
Dorsolateral anterior thalamic nucleus	0.18 ± 0.009	0.182 ± 0.011	<u>0.199 ± 0.015</u>	0.208 ± 0.017	F=15.961 p=0.0008	F=5.821 p=0.027	F=2.224 p=0.153
Dorsomedial anterior thalamic nucleus	0.1 ± 0.007	0.089 ± 0.004	<u>0.113 ± 0.016</u>	<u>0.095 ± 0.011</u>	F=7.723 p=0.012	F=20.885 p=0.0002	F=1.552 p=0.229
Lateral striatum	<u>0.558 ± 0.053</u>	<u>0.56 ± 0.041</u>	0.527 ± 0.034	0.513 ± 0.033	F=5.091 p=0.037	F=0.916 p=0.351	F=1.953 p=0.179
Lateral hypothalamus	0.142 ± 0.009	0.135 ± 0.011	<u>0.156 ± 0.012</u>	<u>0.141 ± 0.008</u>	F=6.726 p=0.018	F=24.059 p=0.0001	F=2.611 p=0.123
Septum	0.184 ± 0.011	0.179 ± 0.013	0.179 ± 0.013	0.168 ± 0.008	F=2.925 p=0.104	F=15.887 p=0.0009	F=1.864 p=0.189
Caudocentral septal area	0.021 ± 0.002	0.023 ± 0.002	0.022 ± 0.002	0.024 ± 0.003	F=1.169 p=0.294	F=8.436 p=0.009	F=0.263 p=0.614
Hypothalamus	0.201 ± 0.017	0.189 ± 0.02	0.206 ± 0.016	0.192 ± 0.017	F=0.37, p=0.551	F=18.959, p=0.0004	F=0.199 p=0.661
Hippocampus	0.538 ± 0.057	0.582 ± 0.088	0.518 ± 0.037	0.566 ± 0.049	F=0.596, p=0.45	F=11.495, p=0.003	F=0.022 p=0.885
Accessory oculomotor nuclei	0.04 ± 0.004	0.039 ± 0.003	0.044 ± 0.004	0.041 ± 0.003	F=3.286, p=0.087	F=5.202, p=0.035	F=1.706 p=0.208
Dorsal part of the PAG #	0.239 ± 0.017	0.27 ± 0.016	0.258 ± 0.028	0.294 ± 0.029			
Medioventral part of the PAG #	0.033 ± 0.004	0.022 ± 0.003	0.039 ± 0.009	0.025 ± 0.002			
Accumbens nucleus ##	0.049 ± 0.005	0.053 ± 0.004	0.054 ± 0.004	0.058 ± 0.002			
Lobule 1 of the cerebellum	0.14 ± 0.011	0.18 ± 0.017	0.133 ± 0.019	0.162 ± 0.018	F=3.009 p=0.1	F=429.64 p<0.0001	F=8.753 p=0.008
Lobule 2 of the cerebellum	<u>0.191 ± 0.018</u>	<u>0.194 ± 0.018</u>	0.156 ± 0.013	0.16 ± 0.009	F=31.278 p<0.0001	F=1.445 p=0.245	F=0.072 p=0.792
Lobule 3 of the cerebellum	0.284 ± 0.033	<u>0.269 ± 0.03</u>	0.234 ± 0.02	0.229 ± 0.017	F=16.885 p=0.0007	F=9.831 p=0.006	F=2.676 p=0.119
Lobule 4 of the cerebellum	<u>0.332 ± 0.031</u>	0.373 ± 0.04	0.284 ± 0.033	0.329 ± 0.031	F=9.953 p=0.005	F=111.734 p<0.0001	F=0.097 p=0.759
Lobule 5 of the cerebellum	0.413 ± 0.047	<u>0.384 ± 0.04</u>	0.375 ± 0.035	0.354 ± 0.036	F=4.662 p=0.045	F=10.006 p=0.005	F=0.303 p=0.589
Lobule 6 of the cerebellum	0.755 ± 0.138	0.735 ± 0.125	0.674 ± 0.096	0.675 ± 0.084	F=2.052 p=0.169	F=0.592 p=0.452	F=0.764 p=0.394
Lobule 7 of the cerebellum	0.458 ± 0.057	0.425 ± 0.048	0.413 ± 0.047	0.389 ± 0.046	F=3.546 p=0.076	F=25.945 p<0.0001	F=0.667 p=0.425

Lobule 8 of the cerebellum	0.522 ± 0.079	0.481 ± 0.074	0.473 ± 0.035	0.442 ± 0.03	F=2.928 p=0.104	F=58.716 p<0.0001	F=1.063 p=0.316
Lobule 9 of the cerebellum	0.527 ± 0.085	0.476 ± 0.083	0.467 ± 0.051	0.436 ± 0.042	F=2.8 p=0.112	F=75.243 p<0.0001	F=4.512 p=0.048
Lobule 10 of the cerebellum	0.295 ± 0.033	0.291 ± 0.031	0.266 ± 0.043	0.263 ± 0.042	F=2.996 p=0.101	F=1.196 p=0.289	F=0.0001 p=0.992
Cerebellar white matter	1.186 ± 0.103	1.055 ± 0.087	1.026 ± 0.089	0.93 ± 0.066	F=13.95 p=0.002	F=188.163 p<0.0001	F=4.425 p=0.05
Cerebellar peduncles	0.084 ± 0.009	0.077 ± 0.005	0.084 ± 0.007	0.076 ± 0.005	F=0.018 p=0.896	F=25.305 p<0.0001	F=0.279 p=0.604
Medial cerebellum nucleus #	0.076 ± 0.006	0.068 ± 0.007	0.07 ± 0.011	0.064 ± 0.006			
Lateral cerebellum nucleus ##	0.018 ± 0.002	0.015 ± 0.001	0.019 ± 0.002	0.015 ± 0.002			
Nucleus of the diagonal band	0.112 ± 0.008	0.114 ± 0.008	0.115 ± 0.007	0.117 ± 0.007	F=0.572 p=0.459	F=4.141 p=0.057	F=0.06 p=0.81
Dorsal paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus #	0.196 ± 0.02	0.183 ± 0.015	0.228 ± 0.05	0.206 ± 0.019			
Striatum	1.37 ± 0.057	1.399 ± 0.059	1.381 ± 0.073	1.38 ± 0.059	F=0.02 p=0.89	F=2.524 p=0.13	F=2.599 p=0.124
Lateral septum #	0.099 ± 0.009	0.117 ± 0.011	0.1 ± 0.007	0.115 ± 0.01			
Interhemispheric regions							
Brain region	LTI quails	STI quails	Statistical values (Line effect)				
Hippocampal commissure	0.032 ± 0.003	0.033 ± 0.005	t=-0.4819, p=0.636				
Pineal gland	0.116 ± 0.015	0.133 ± 0.016	t=-2.4388, p=0.0253				
Pituitary gland	0.29 ± 0.05	0.281 ± 0.052	t=0.3913, p=0.7				